

USE OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING THE SCIENCE OF EDUCATION

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Abstract.

This article talks about the pedagogical technologies necessary for the pedagogue to effectively teach the science of "Education" and the prerequisites for their use.

Keywords: Pedagogy, technology, science, field, network, education, knowledge, youth.

"Pedagogy" and "Technology" are one of the fields that have been developing and improving for many years. Over time, these areas are becoming a separate branch of science, for example, Pedagogy as a science begins to take shape during the time of the famous Czech pedagogue Jan Amos Comenius, in the 17th century. He made a great contribution to the field of pedagogy with his work "Great Didactics". The emergence of "technology" as a science - in the 17th century, the emergence of industrial production was the reason for the rapid development of metallurgy, mechanical engineering, including the production of industrial equipment, steam locomotives, firearms. The origin of the term "Technology" goes back to ancient Greece, like "Pedagogy". Technology - "techne" means art, "logos" means learning. "Pedagogy" means "paidagogike" (paída) - child, (gogos) - leader. Now, let's talk about pedagogical technology. Pedagogical technology is the organization of pedagogical activity with high skill. Pedagogical technology is a narrower concept compared to technology, which implies learning the theoretical and practical foundations of education with skill and art.¹ Due to the lack of a clearly defined description of pedagogical technology, this term has been interpreted in different ways. According to V. P. Bepalko, pedagogical technology is the systematic and sequential application of a pre-planned educational process to practice. N. Sayidakhmedov describes the pedagogical technology as follows: it is the process of the teacher influencing students in certain conditions with the help of teaching tools, and as a product of this activity, they form predetermined personal qualities.² The term pedagogical technology appeared in the United States in the middle of the 20th century, and at first it was not called this, but in the 1940s and 50s it was called "Educational technology". This phrase is applied to teaching using technical means.

There are two necessary factors of pedagogical technology:

- Systematic;
- Efficiency.

It is no secret that pedagogical technology is becoming an integral part of education. Pedagogical technology was created on this basis in order to integrate it further into the field of education. This science is the science of creating and applying a reproducible effective

¹ S.I.Mirhayitova "Pedagogical technology". Tashkent-2020

² N.X.Avliyaqulov, N.N.Musayeva "Pedagogical technology". A boston of thought. Tashkent-2012.

educational process that is goal-oriented, controlled, guaranteed to achieve the planned results in the conditions of mass education.

Pedagogical technologies are divided into the following types according to the main method used:

- explanation;
- demonstrative;
- creative methods;
- game method;
- informative educational method and others.

The more interesting and meaningful pedagogic technologies teachers use in organizing the lesson process, the more eager the student is to master the subject. Now we will list some of such technologies, connecting them to the subjects of "Education" science. The 12th topic of the 5th grade "Education" textbook is dedicated to "My goal is my passion". During the course of the lesson, the teacher first explains to the students the need to set the right goal and act accordingly with strong enthusiasm shows examples to the students and gives stories related to the topic. In the part of strengthening the lesson, the pedagogue can use the "Enthusiasm table". In this case, the first "no desire" column lists harmful habits that destroy the goal, and the second, "there is a desire" column is empty for the reader to fill in with a word that has the opposite meaning to the first column. will be In addition, by using the "Motivational Ladder" method on this topic, the pedagogue can help the student to choose goals clearly and correctly.³ In this case, the student will have to write his goals in relation to his age. Now let's see what methods can be used effectively in teaching the science of "Education" for high school students. If we focus on topic 13 of the 9th grade "Education" textbook "*Succeeding in a knowledge-based society*", the pedagogue focuses on this topic on the value of an educated citizen in a knowledge-based society and encourages students to contribute to the development of the country by acquiring more knowledge induces swelling. In order to strengthen the topic in a lively way, it would be appropriate to organize a theater on the topic with the participation of students as a practical activity, and through this, find a solution to the problem from the students themselves. In order to increase the sociability of the students and strengthen their cooperation during the lesson, the teacher divides the students into four groups and assigns one of the texts under the following heading in the book to each of them, and gives them 5-7 minutes to read the text and think about each other time determines:

- Positive thinking in scope
- People management skills
- Interaction with people
- Making decisions and making conclusions

At the end of the allotted time, the students express their opinions about their topic. This pedagogical technology has a positive effect on the speech and socialization of high school students while serving to develop their thinking ability.

In conclusion, it would be appropriate if pedagogues use pedagogical technologies to make the lesson processes interesting and meaningful, and to make the lesson solid.

³ 5th grade "Education" textbook. Tashkent-2020

References:

1. N.Kh.Avliyakov, N.N.Musayeva "Pedagogical technology". A boston of thought. Tashkent-2012
2. S.I. Mirhayitova "Pedagogical technology". Tashkent-2020
3. 5th grade "Education" textbook. Pages 42-46. Tashkent-2020
4. Yakubova Sh. The system of forming a positive world view in students through the educational teachings of eastern thinkers // Procedia of Philosophical and Pedagogical Sciences, – Portugaliya. Number - 10. Volume-2. 2023. P. 81-85. Issue-10. ISSN 2795-546X.